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Classification and operating modes of backup energy supply sources of mobile networks

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Abstract: This article provides information on the classification and operating modes of backup energy supply sources of mobile networks. Depending on the electromagnetic processes occurring in autonomous inverters, they are divided into: current inverter, resonance inverter, and voltage inverters. In resonant inverters, with a large inductance in the load, together with other reactive elements, it forms an oscillation circuit and voltage resonance occurs.

Keywords: Alternating current, voltage, phase, inverter, electromagnetic processes, generator, commutation, choke, thyristor

INTRODUCTION

Converters that convert direct current into alternating current and operate on an autonomous load are called autonomous inverters. Depending on the number of voltage phases at their outputs, they are divided into single-, three-, and multi-phase inverters. Depending on the construction of the circuits, they are divided into zero-output, bridge-type and half-bridge-type.

Depending on the electromagnetic processes occurring in autonomous inverters, they are divided into: current inverter, resonance inverter, and voltage inverters.

A choke with a large inductance must be connected to the input of the current inverter circuit. In this case, the capacitor participating in the switching is charged aperiodically, the input current is ideally smoothed and continuous. That is, the source works in the current generator mode. Depending on the

connection of the switching capacitor in current inverters to the load, they are divided into series, parallel and series-parallel inverters.

In resonant inverters, with a large inductance in the load, together with other reactive elements, it forms an oscillation circuit and voltage resonance occurs. Thyristors in such schemes are closed after the value of the anode current reaches zero. The source powering resonant inverters can operate in current generator or voltage generator modes. If the source providing the resonant inverter works as a voltage generator, it is called an open-input resonant inverter. It is called a closed-input resonant generator when the source works as a current generator. Such inverters are divided into series, parallel, series-parallel, as mentioned above. In voltage inverters, the supply source acts as a voltage generator and its internal resistance must be small. If its internal resistance is large, then a capacitor with a large capacity is connected to the input of the inverter.

Single-phase parallel current inverter. The thyristors in the circuit work in pairs, that is, V1, V2, and V3, V4 (Fig. 1). For example, when opening pulses are applied to V1 and V2, they open and current flows through the following circuit: positive potential of input voltage U_d , inductance L_d , thyristor V1, load Z_w , thyristor V2, negative potential of input voltage U_d . After 180° ellrad. with respect to the opening time of the thyristors given above, an opening pulse is given to the thyristors V3 and V4, and current flows through the following circuit: positive potential of the input voltage U_d , inductance L , thyristor V3, load Z_{IO} , thyristor V4, input voltage U_d negative potential. It can be seen that during one reversal cycle, alternating current of the opposite direction passes through the load twice. The forms of currents and voltages in the elements of the circuit are shown in diagrams, respectively (Fig. 5)

Figure 1. Operation of thyristors.

The following equivalent circuit is used to calculate the circuit:

Figure 2. A simple scheme of the filter.

The principle diagram of a single-phase zero-output shunt diode parallel current inverter is shown

in Fig. 3, and its operation diagrams are shown in Fig.

Figure 3. The principle diagram of the current inverter

From the time of the opening pulse to the V1 thyristor, the current flows through the following circuit: U_d is the positive potential of the voltage, L_d is the inductance, so, the primary winding, D1, the interrupting diode, S is the capacitor, V2 is the thyristor, U_d is the negative potential of the voltage. (Fig. 3) After 180 degrees, an opening pulse is given to the thyristor V2, and it opens and current flows through the following circuit: U_d is the positive potential of the voltage, L_d is the inductance, oz , the primary circuit, D2 is the breaking diode, S is the capacitor, V2 is the thyristor, U_d is the negative potential of the voltage.

Due to the current passing through the primary coils, the variable E.Y.K. in the secondary coil. is formed. This causes alternating current to flow through the load. After the capacitor current 1S in the circuit in the inverter with R-L load is working, the diodes D1, D2 are closed, which is possible to discharge the capacitor.

So, from this moment on, the value of the voltage in the capacitor remains unchanged. This situation makes it possible to use a low-capacity capacitor in an inverter operating at a low frequency. (compared to the absence of diodes D1 and D2) Another good feature of using diodes D1 and D2 is that the delay time is relatively large. This can be seen from the UB2 voltage diagram. Therefore, the demand for usable thyristor is reduced. The order of operation of thyristors in the scheme (Fig. 5) is similar to the order of operation of three-phase bridge rectifier thyristors. Therefore, to open the thyristors, the thyristors are opened with the help of control pulses, one of which is narrower and one is shifted from the other by 60 el.fad. or one is wider than 60 el.degree.

The operation of the circuit is similar to that of a single-phase parallel current inverter. Due to intervalve commutation, when a thyristor in one group is opened, the open thyristors of this group are closed due to the discharge current of the capacitor. For example: when working with V1, V4, the capacitor S1 will have poles as shown in the picture. When the V3 thyristor in this group opens, the V1 thyristor closes as a result of the discharge current passing through the V1, V3 thyristors due to the energy collected in

the capacitor S1.

Figure 4. Current inverter operation diagrams.

Figure 5. Operation of thyristors

Figure 6. Functional diagrams of thyristors

Depending on the state of the network and the size of the load, UTM can work in different modes: network, autonomous, Bypass, etc.

Conclusion

Network mode - the mode of supplying the load from the network energy. It works in the UTM network mode, provided that the network voltage and load are within the limits of the fixed deviation and do not exceed the maximum allowed. In this mode, the following occurs:

- filtering of impulse and high-frequency network noises;
- change of alternating current energy in the network to direct current energy using a rectifier and power factor correction scheme;
- change direct current energy to alternating current energy with stable parameters using an inverter;
- charge the battery using a battery charger.

Autonomous mode - the mode of providing the load with energy from the battery. When the network voltage parameters deviate from the permitted limits or in cases of complete loss, the UTM battery switches to autonomous supply mode through the step-up converter and inverter at the expense of battery energy. It switches to mains mode when the mains power is restored.

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